

MEASURES TO PROTECT 110 KV AND CITY POWER NETWORKS FROM DAMAGE AND SHORT CIRCUITS

Turniyozov Zuxriddin.

Master of the Department of Electric Power Navoi State Mining and
Technological University

Shirinov Sohibjon.

Master of the Department of Electric Power Navoi State Mining and
Technological University

Xushvaqtov Jo'rabek.

Department of "Electric Power Engineering" Student of group 5a-21EE

Annotation. In recent years, our country has undergone radical changes aimed at developing the economy and improving the living standards of the population. Free economic zones, technoparks and clusters are being established in various regions of the country. At the same time, more attention is paid to the protection of the environment and environmental sustainability than ever before. Such rapid growth in all spheres of society and state life, first of all, leads to an increase in the demand for electricity.

Key words: Electricity, power, thermal power plants, waste, electricity tariffs. Loss of electricity in the networks reduces losses during long-distance transmission. High voltage is associated with a variety of losses. The crown deterge near high voltage wires is accompanied by unusual noise and noise. The bending often causes corrosion of the wires. [1,2]

One of the main indicators of the efficiency and economic efficiency of electric networks is the loss of electricity in the technical design and operation of electrical equipment and divices. Constant failure to supply power to operating processes and power lines results in excessive electricity losses. This is due to the currant load of network elements.

Network elements:

$$I = \frac{\sqrt{P^2 + (Q + \Delta Q)^2}}{\sqrt{3} U}$$

When delivering electricity to consumers, it must be uninterrupted, reliable and qualityю. But lately this process is not enough at present, measures are being developet to minimize the possible solution to this problem. Operation of the mains is mainly taken into account for active and reactive power losses and losses in the grid.

Network power loss:

$$\Delta P_{\text{л}} = \frac{P^2 + Q^2}{U_{\text{H}}^2} * R$$

Network reactive power supply:

$$\Delta Q_{\text{л}} = \frac{P^2 + Q^2}{U_{\text{H}}^2} * X$$

Energy loss:

$$\Delta A_{\text{л}} = \Delta P_{\text{л}} * \tau$$

Where τ is the maximum annual working time of consumers.

Basically, it is possible to reduce vastage by doing the following sequence of work.

1. The power grid is the basis of the system approach, which includes evaluating the effects of reactive power losses and providing efficient, quality, and uninterrupted power supply;
2. To give a mathematical explanation of existing power (Active and reactive) parameters of a transmission line;
3. Development of statistical methodology for structural analysis of power and energy losses;
4. Reduce the impact of reactive power loss measures on the feasibility and feasibility of their implementation (Transmission lines)

In order to insure reliable operation of the power grid, our main goal in reducing waste is to analyses the losses associated with the emergence of the crown line in

our conjure, as well as to develop up-to-date universal recommendations for reducing power losses for each crown.

Reduction of flexible and active capacities will have a direct impact on consumers operating modes. If there is stability, then energy losses will be reduced, and electricity consumption and transport costs will also decrease. It is necessary to analyze the state of electrical circuits to determine the sources of wastage in the reactive energy.

By configuration, and structure. Subsequent assessments are made under each system. The effect of the power losses on the transmission lines in the subsystems isolated by the electricity network configuration is evaluated.

Energy losses, naturally and in terms of production, distribution and consumption, are not the same as those used for energy consumption. Because their costs are includes in higher costs and annual maintenance costs.

Any technical measures to reduce losses are costly. Losses are always lowered, and vice versa, with smaller funds available. It is possible to know all the measures to reduce losses to 2 groups. Organizational and technical. Organizational arrangements do not require overtime, or over-budgeting.

Organizational measures include:

1. Increase voltage depending on available tools and devices.
2. Extension of service life and improvement of power supply equipment repair.
3. Matching annual and dale load schedules with the same power consumption and so on.

Technical measures require large additional costs. To calculate loss reduction, these measures are summarized as follows.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

1. Switching the network to high rated voltage: U_{nom}
2. Using wires with cross-sectional surfaces.
3. Replacement overloaded transformers.
4. Installation of compensation devices.

5. Technics measures to reduce losses.

It is advisable to be based on the relevant economic calculations. [1,3] To determine the cause of electrical losses, a sample of control measurements and monthly calculations of power meters over a period of 4 to 6 years.

Technical losses are, in turn, divided into reactive losses and losses in power lines. Later, no other indicators of reactive energy loss are required. At the same time, the structural analysis of energy losses takes into account the strength of the lines this affects the energy lost along the line.

Structural analysis is performed in the following sequence. [5]

1. The ratio of technical losses to uninterrupted over supply to the network is determined by the nominal voltage classes.
2. It analyzes the proportion of jet losses in transmission lines.
3. The dynamics of loading and contingent constant losses are studied.
4. Factors for loading of reactive power coefficients and power transforms are analyzed.
5. The sources and causes of loss of electricity are identified.

An overview of the methodology proposed for the structural analyses of reactive losses is given in an example used in the electronic mode analysis.

Dynamics of power supply technical losses is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of the mitigation measures this should be determinant for each class of nominal voltage.

Analysis shows that if electricity losses do not change over 5 years, the transmission system does not solve the problem of leakage, or the measures taken are ineffective.

Technical losses of electricity are higher in 10 kV networks, and analysis of the schematic state of the network confirms the results it is surefire advisable to revive these networks for further analysis.

Dynamics of technical reactive loses and the ratio of reactive energy transmitted through the network allows estimation of the accuracy of reactive

energy. If technical losses of reactive energy are associated with reactive energy transmitted through the network, then real bite the economic part can be argued, otherwise a large metrological component of losses will be present.

Special to protect the power line from damage devices are used. Lightning ropes to protect them, lightning reflectors, tubular dischargers, and earthing devices. Substations are the main link in the power grid system. Depending on their location in the electricity system, the city, district electricity also as a branch substation or an industrial enterprise substation referred to. The district substation mainly consumes energy from the district power grid and energy to industry, agriculture and other consumers provides. The primary voltage of district substations is 220, 110 kV the secondary voltage will be 35, 20, 10 or 6 kV.

Power dissipation load on any element of the electrical network depends on its nature and its change during the construction process. It does not change operating with load, ΔP for a period of time in with active power dissipation. The wasted energy is determined as follows:

$$\Delta W = \Delta P \cdot t$$

III. CONCLUSION

Wey can conclude that in some substations, an active energy fossil can be reduced to 16,8% with a reactive energy loss of up to 20%. Based on the results of the study, wey can draw the following conic lusions.

1. Loss of jet energy has a significant impact on the efficiency and releability of the power grid, and their over lapping levels lead to a decrease in the profits of the tsclot network .
2. A method of analizing the circuits in the case of the current state of the elektrikcal network, which allows to determini the in fluence of thous ands of reactive energy losses, has be in proposed.

3. He has developed a statistical method for the structural analysis of reactive power losses in the operating conditions of the data used to identify energy losses.
4. This method allows us to identify used losses and identify their high values and causes.
5. Active energy loss reduction is also reflected in the distribution complexes.

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